

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT SOLUTION

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Abstract— it is an android application. This allows the creation of different users. User types can be customized. The documents can be uploaded as images or PDF's. They can then assign the documents to friends. Invite friends and create group of them. User can create annotation to the documents highlight or make notes on the document. These documents can be shared.

Keywords—PDF, image, group, document

I. INTRODUCTION

Document Management Solution is an android application. The application is developed for an Institute. In this android application there is one super admin which is responsible for creating user. User can be student, faculty, director, HOD. All users can upload the documents in the form of PDF or image. Higher authorities like HOD, Faculty can approve or reject the requests from the students. When student or faculty uploads the document a push notification should be pop-up. DMS maintains the database such that date of uploading the signature and date of uploading document is stored.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

IT Moodle [1] is application through which faculty can upload the study material, assignments etc. so that all students can easily access this data on their respective accounts. Different accounts for different users are created by the super user. Also they can provide link for uploading the assignments to the students. It also provides chat forum facility.

Advantages:

- Reduces paper work.
- Provides security.
- Students and faculty can easily interact with each other.

Disadvantages:

- Student doesn't know whether his uploaded document is seen or not by the faculty.
- Student cannot upload any document other than study.
- Pop-up notification is not generated after uploading new documents.

Ritage [2] is application through which student can access their academic activities through their respective accounts. Student can see their monthly attendance subject wise. Faculty fills the student's monthly attendance through this application. Student will also able to know about the extra curriculum activities in institute. Faculty can easily get the personal details of students.

Advantages:

- Easy to handle.
- Reduces paper work.
- Reduces time consumption.
- Provides security.

Disadvantages:

- Student cannot upload any application document.
- Doesn't pop up any notification.

Share File application [3] is an existing application which is used to share the file among the multiple user. It will ensure the modification, saving, sending and retrieval of files. It is an android application which is having following advantages and disadvantages:

Advantages:

- Maximum size upto 10 GB for file upload
- Can be accessed from multiple devices (PC, Mac or mobile)
- Searching option within documents
- Mobile application for phone as well as tablet
- Settings for security purpose

Disadvantages:

- It is costly nearly up to \$29.95/month
- Multiple users cannot be created

Pinpoint [4] is an application which provides all the features required for Document Management Solution. When you want a particular document, It creates a viewable image in a PDF format in that user can add comments and markups. So by using this feature it will save a lot of time of user.

Advantages-

- It will keep the record of who will use which document.
- It will be compatible to mobile also.

Disadvantages-

- It will not available on weekends.

- Does not provide immediate help to user.

In [5] File Hold is a self-hosted document management system used for businesses which are using Windows system only. In this software Filing documents is very easy and can be done in many ways by the user. It will provide drag and drop facility for user means user can drag and drop files which are already present in the computer. We can add the document using Microsoft Office with just a click of a button.

Advantages:

- Remote access for employees means it is easy to access from anywhere.
- File Hold provides security with the help of various measures such as "read only" and "system administration."

Disadvantages:

- Customer can contact or interact via email and online.
- It is so much costly because the cost for software and its installation will cost at least \$5,000.

Zohodocs application [6] is an online tool which allows you to share and collaborate a file with friends or group of members. User can easily access the files which are shared and collaborate with colleagues who are located in different time zones. User can perform many functions such as Archive files, Attach files, Send Email, Import/Export etc.

Advantages:

- It is secure.
- It is having Low cost and requires less Maintenance.
- Easy to Use and can be accessed from anywhere
- Provide back-up facility.
- We can attach files and send email to this application.
- We can share file with friends in real time.

By reading and analyzing IEEE conference paper by Nakamura.s, Chiba.s, Kaminaga.s, Yokoyama.s, Miyadera.y "Development of a Topic-Centered Adaptive "Document Management System" [7] we got the idea of centrally storage of the data which is easy to maintain and use. The above all specified problem will motivate us to design an android application that will overcome most of the problems in the current system.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

We plan to provide the android application which reduces the paper work in the existing system. Also we will provide the online availability of the document which is centrally available at one place. We have also plan to provide the security using Github (SmartGit).

A. The objectives of the proposed system are

- Reduced the paper work.
- Reduced operational time.
- Increased accuracy and reliability.
- Data security.

- Online availability of document.

B. Scope of the implemented system:

This application is useful and limited to the RIT. It may be extend to other educational institutes

C. Diagrams

Fig: Flow Diagram

Fig: Modular chart

D. Working

Document Management solution is an android application. It will provide simple GUI which is easy to use and reduces lots of work of user. There will be 4 different user of this application which is Admin, HOD, Faculty and Student. Each user will need to register for this application. There are different registration forms for different users. Admin will register only once for this application and there will be only one admin for this application. For registering to application user need to provide username, password, mobile no, address and role which is by default set means when user click on student register image button then role is by default student. After registration user need to login for application by specifying username, password and role. If user is already registered then he/she does not need to register again he just need to provide username and password for login to the application When user login to application as student then he/she will have following tasks:

- Request for leave application

- Check the status for either leave is sanctioned or not.

When user login to application as an admin then he/she will have following tasks:

- Create group of registered student
- Assign admin to that group

When user login to application as a HOD then he/she will have following tasks:

- View the different request which comes from different student
- Give reply to student request that is either approved or rejected.

After registration message will be sent to that user on the basis of registration details. When student upload any document as like leave application then pop-up notification will be generated and it will be send to HOD.

IV. ANALYSIS

Previously there is no such android application for document management solution. We cannot send request for leave and for other reason to HOD and faculty through android application. Data is centrally stored but can't access using android application. There is no facility for modification of data in previous system.

In Document Management Solution data is centrally available and can be accessed by different users of these applications. HOD and faculty can modify the content of data and approve and reject the request coming from student

After implementation of this project all the data is centrally stored and accessed by different users by using android application. It will reduce lot of paper work in the organization and it will be easy to use.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Conclusion:

The project entitled document management solution will be done in an effective manner. Document management solution is an efficient, time saving and easy way to upload, modify and view the documents by creating the different groups in application.

Future work:

This application may further applicable for all institute.

In future it will include E-mail facility.

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